

BIM ADOPTION FOR STRUCTURAL ENGINEERING DESIGN

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Abstract

The intention of the Thesis is to exploit the developments, benefits, and applications of "Building Information Modelling" (BIM) adoption in general, and with focus to the structural design discipline for cast in place reinforced concrete buildings.

BIM has been mainly considered as a new way of designing, constructing, and operating a building or infrastructure. It has been identified as generating bigger opportunities for higher efficiency, optimization of resources and in general better management during all the life cycle of a facility. BIM increases the digitization of processes, offering integrated and collaborative technologies for design, construction, and operation.

To understand BIM and its benefits, it is necessary to take into evaluation all the phases of a project. Higher initial cost for design can bring to lower ones for construction and operation. Creating data rich digital models, helps to better predict and coordinate the construction phases and operation of a building. One of the main limitations identified in BIM adoption is the lack of knowledge and qualified skilled professionals. Specific disciplines like structural and mechanical design depend, if the main contractor, owner, general contractor, or architect are making use or require applying BIM for their projects. The presence of a supporting or mandatory BIM policy, can then finally conclude its adoption.

"Business Process Re-engineering" (BPR) allows to analyse actual "AS-IS" processes within AEC firms, vision steps through the ones BIM can be implemented, and consolidate "TO-BE" processes that can be developed with time. Applying BIM for structural engineering design, allows managers and owners to predict costs better and faster, supports a correct scheduling of constructions works, contributes to clash detections, facilitates future interventions during the building operation, reduces costs for construction works and in general contributes to an integrated vision of the facility.

Many realizations have been identified in the BIM adoption for projects with success in the last decades. Structural Engineers are very positive to the BIM adoption compared to the other disciplines. It is noted that more you make use of BIM, more it is likely you will appreciate its application also in the future projects. Its adoption it is identified to generate benefits in all stages of a project. Higher quality, reduced costs, reliable designs, accurate quantities, automated processes and drawing management, 3D virtual visualization and better site coordination, are just some of the benefits identified.

For the scope of the Thesis, some workflows for structural design are built, and BPR applied to improve them towards BIM adoption. Structural design BIM enabled software, Autodesk Revit - Robot SA 2021, Autodesk Revit - SOFiSTiK 2021, ProSap Professional v21 and Tekla Structural Designer (TSD) - Tekla Structures (TS) 2021, are introduced, analysed, and applied in integrated workflows to some Case Studies, and subsequently evaluated based on some defined criteria. A new BIM SDWAM ("BIM Structural Design's Workflow Assessment Model") is proposed and applied for the evaluation of the presented workflows. Discussions and conclusions are presented in the last Chapter.

Dissertation:

<https://bimaplus.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/2021-ErsilioTushaj-Dissertation.pdf>

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/U3PY1JcReQg>

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